

Supporting information

Hydrogen Evolution Reaction Activity in $\text{Mo}_2\text{TiC}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene Derived from $\text{Mo}_2\text{TiAlC}_2$ MAX Phase: Insights from Compositional Transformations

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KEYWORDS: MAX phases, MXenes, hydrogen evolution reaction, 2D materials, electrocatalysis

Figure S1. Thermogravimetric analysis curve of the $\text{Mo}_2\text{TiC}_2\text{T}_x$ sample performed in an Ar atmosphere at a 100 ml/min flow and a heating rate of 10 °C/min.

Table S1. Peak positions, full-width at half maximum (FWHM), concentration and assignement for XPS data for sample $\text{Mo}_2\text{TiAlC}_2$.

Region	BE (eV)	FWHM (eV)	At. %	Assignement
Ti $2p_{3/2}$ (Ti $2p_{1/2}$)	454.2 (460.2)	1.00 (1.50)	34.2	$\text{Mo}_2\text{TiAlC}_2$
	455.5 (461.5)	2.45 (3.67)	44.2	$\text{Mo}_2\text{Ti}^{\text{II}}\text{AlC}_2$
	457.9 (463.9)	2.40 (3.60)	21.6	$\text{Mo}_2\text{Ti}^{\text{III}}\text{AlC}_2$
Mo $3d_{5/2}$ (Mo $3d_{3/2}$)	227.7 (230.9)	0.96 (0.96)	100	$\text{Mo}_2\text{TiAlC}_2$
C 1s	282.4	1.63	22.0	$\text{Mo}_2\text{TiAlC}_2$
	284.8	1.45	69.0	Adv. C-C
	286.0	1.76	9.0	Adv. C-O
Al $2p_{3/2}$	74.3	2.40	100.0	$\text{Mo}_2\text{TiAlC}_2$
O 1s	531.4	2.66	100.0	Adv. O-C

Table S2. Peak positions, full-width at half maximum (FWHM), concentration and assignment for XPS data for sample $\text{Mo}_2\text{TiC}_2\text{T}_x$.

Region	BE (eV)	FWHM (eV)	At. %	Assignment
Ti $2p_{3/2}$ (Ti $2p_{1/2}$)	454.8 (460.8)	1.11 (1.63)	11.1	$\text{Mo}_2\text{TiAlC}_2$
	455.4 (461.2)	2.2 (3.3)	35.0	$\text{Mo}_2\text{Ti}^{\text{II}}\text{AlC}_2$
	457.6 (463.6)	2.39 (3.58)	21.3	$\text{Mo}_2\text{Ti}^{\text{III}}\text{AlC}_2$
	458.6 (464.5)	3.00 (4.50)	32.6	TiO_2
Mo $3d_{5/2}$ (Mo $3d_{3/2}$)	228.0 (231.2)	1.03 (1.03)	100	$\text{Mo}_2\text{TiAlC}_2$
C 1s	282.7	1.05	14.6	$\text{Mo}_2\text{TiAlC}_2$
	284.8	1.49	70.8	Adv. C-C
	286.0	1.70	9.0	Adv. C-O
	288.2	2.25	5.6	Adv. O-C=O
O 1s	530.2	1.48	45.5	M-O
	531.3	2.36	39.6	Adv. O=C
	533.7	2.58	14.9	Adv. O-C
F 1s	685.1	2.36	100.0	M-F

Figure S2. a) Chronoamperometry curve for $\text{Mo}_2\text{TiC}_2\text{T}_x$ sample in 0.5M H_2SO_4 electrolyte. b) Nyquist plots of $\text{Mo}_2\text{TiC}_2\text{T}_x$ sample in 0.5M H_2SO_4 at various times. The blue curve represent a fit of the experimental data.

Table S3. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy parameters obtained from data fitting.

Sample	R_s (Ω)	R_{CT} (Ω)	R_L (Ω)	Y_{01} ($\text{s}^{-n}\Omega^{-1}$)	n_1	L_1 (H)
$\text{Mo}_2\text{TiC}_2\text{T}_x$	13.05	32.75	348.90	4.23E-05	0.87	0.72
$\text{Mo}_2\text{TiC}_2\text{T}_x$ 13h	13.07	22.47	82.10	7.12E-05	0.95	0.90
$\text{Mo}_2\text{TiC}_2\text{T}_x$ 53h	13.00	51.22	395.05	4.47E-06	0.94	0.49

Figure S3. X-ray photoelectron spectra of $\text{Mo}_2\text{TiC}_2\text{T}_x$ 13h sample. a) survey spectrum; b) Ti 2p spectrum; c) Mo 3d spectrum; d) C 1s spectrum; e) Al 2p spectrum, f) O 1s spectrum and g) F 1s spectrum.

Table S4. Peak positions, full-width at half maximum (FWHM), concentration and assignment for XPS data for sample Mo₂TiC₂T_x 13h.

Region	BE (eV)	FWHM (eV)	At. %	Assignment
Ti 2p _{3/2} (Ti 2p _{1/2})	454.2 (460.2)	1.20 (1.81)	58.2	Mo ₂ TiAlC ₂
	455.4 (461.4)	2.00 (3.0)	32.1	Mo ₂ Ti ^{II} AlC ₂
	457.8 (463.8)	2.40 (3.60)	9.7	Mo ₂ Ti ^{III} AlC ₂
Mo 3d _{5/2} (Mo 3d _{3/2})	228.2 (231.4)	1.08 (1.08)	13.6	Mo ₂ TiAlC ₂
	229.0 (232.2)	0.79 (0.76)	56.5	MoO ₂ (screened)
	230.6 (233.9)	2.27 (2.22)	20.0	MoO ₂ (unscreened)
	232.9 (235.5)	1.39 (1.39)	9.9	MoO ₃
C 1s	283.1	0.82	26.2	Mo ₂ TiAlC ₂
	284.7	1.28	36.9	Adv. C-C
	285.8	2.37	32.6	Adv. C-O
	288.7	1.72	4.3	Adv. O-C=O
O 1s	530.0	1.04	42.5	M-O
	531.3	2.28	45.1	Adv. O=C
	533.0	2.50	12.4	Adv. O-C
F 1s	684.8	1.47	100.0	M-F

Table S5. Peak positions, full-width at half maximum (FWHM), concentration and assignement for XPS data for sample Mo₂TiC₂T_x 53h.

Region	BE (eV)	FWHM (eV)	At. %	Assignment
Ti 2p _{3/2} (Ti 2p _{1/2})	454.5 (460.5)	1.19 (1.72)	48.1	Mo ₂ TiAlC ₂
	455.3 (461.3)	2.00 (3.00)	39.8	Mo ₂ Ti ^{II} AlC ₂
	457.4 (463.4)	2.20 (3.30)	12.1	Mo ₂ Ti ^{III} AlC ₂
Mo 3d _{5/2} (Mo 3d _{3/2})	228.0 (231.1)	0.70 (0.70)	6.4	Mo ₂ TiAlC ₂
	228.9 (232.1)	0.77 (0.76)	64.1	MoO ₂ (screened)
	230.4 (233.8)	2.51 (2.22)	21.1	MoO ₂ (unscreened)
	232.9 (235.5)	1.21 (1.21)	8.4	MoO ₃
C 1s	283.1	0.93	30.8	Mo ₂ TiAlC ₂
	284.7	1.24	34.3	Adv. C-C
	286.0	2.04	27.6	Adv. C-O
	288.9	1.78	7.3	Adv. O-C=O
O 1s	530.1	0.88	40.5	M-O
	531.3	2.28	41.1	Adv. O=C
	533.3	1.95	18.4	Adv. O-C

Figure S4. X-ray photoelectron spectra of $\text{Mo}_2\text{TiC}_2\text{T}_x$ 53h sample. a) survey spectrum; b) Ti 2p spectrum; c) Mo 3d spectrum; d) C 1s spectrum; e) Al 2p spectrum, f) O 1s spectrum and g) F 1s spectrum.